

BEHAVIOUR OF CHLORONITROBENZENES WITH HYDRAZINE AND HYDRAZINE DERIVATIVES. PART XI. SUBSTITUTED 1-HYDROXY- 1 : 2 : 3-BENZOTRIAZOLES AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

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A few 1-hydroxy-1:2:3-benzotriazoles have been obtained by condensation of halogenopolynitrobenzenes with hydrazine hydrate or base-catalysed cyclisation of substituted nitrophenylhydrazines. Where formation of more than one product is possible, only one triazole derivative can be isolated. Structures to these compounds have also been assigned.

It has been shown in Part III of the series (Joshi and Deorha, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 545) that triazole formation can take place in two ways with nitrophenylhydrazines having both NO₂ groups in *ortho* position to the hydrazino group, the benzene ring being unsymmetrically substituted. Actually only one compound was isolated from the reaction product. Our previous findings (*loc. cit.*) have been confirmed in case of 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-(Ia), 4-chloro-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-(Ib) and 2:4:6-trinitro-3-methyl-(Ic) phenylhydrazines. From each of them two isomeric hydroxybenzotriazoles, i.e., (IIa) and (IIIa) from (Ia), (IIb) and (IIIb) from (Ib), and (IIc) and (IIIc) from (Ic) could be expected, but only one from each has been isolated.

To assign definite structure to each of the hydroxybenzotriazoles formed, the nitro group present in the molecule is replaced by a halogen atom and the identity of the dihalogenotriazole so formed is established. Thus, the triazole from (Ia) on reduction of the nitro group and subsequent replacement of the amino group by a bromine atom furnishes a dibromomethylhydroxybenzotriazole; the methyl group in this compound can be either in 5 or 7 position. It is, however, identical with the product obtained by replacing the nitro group with a bromine atom in 4-bromo-6-nitro-7-methyl-1-hydroxy-1:2:3-benzotriazole. As in the latter compound (which is formed by cyclisation of 6-bromo-2:4-dinitro-3-methylphenylhydrazine) the methyl group is in position 7, the product of cyclisation of (Ia) should also have the methyl group in that position (*i.e.*, 7) and therefore must be (IIIa).

Following a similar procedure, the triazoles from (Ib) and (Ic) have been assigned structures (IIIb) and (IIIc) respectively (Table IV).

It appears from the above that in all cases, where the reaction can take two alternative courses, the nitro group adjacent to the methyl group is involved in the cyclisation.

Solutions of hydroxytriazoles in ethanol or of their sodium or ammonium salts in water form precipitates with soluble salts of silver, lead, mercury, and barium. Those obtained from hydroxytriazoles having no nitro group are colorless; others vary in colour from yellow to dark red.

The silver salts of hydroxybenzotriazoles are very useful. These are obtained in pure condition easily; when decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid these form silver halide in quantitative yields. The silver halide can be freed of the triazole by washing with ethanol. During the present work this reaction has been utilised for determining the molecular weights of the different hydroxybenzotriazoles. 6-Chloro-4-nitro- and 6-bromo-4-nitro-1-hydroxy-1:2:3-benzotriazoles afford deep red precipitates with minute quantities of soluble silver salts. These can therefore be employed for the detection of silver, even in traces, in presence of other metals, and have been successfully tried as spot test reagents for silver. Further work on the use of these reagents in inorganic analyses is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

The triazoles, described in Tables I and II, were prepared by Methods I and II reported earlier (Joshi and Deorha, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

S. No.	Halogenonitrobenzene used.	1-Hydroxy-1:2:3-benzotriazole formed.	Phenylhydrazine used.
1.	1:2-Dibromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	4-Bromo-6-nitro-7-methyl-	2-Bromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-
2.	2-Chloro-1-bromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	4-Chloro-6-nitro-7-methyl-	2-Chloro-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-
3.	1:4-Dibromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-	6-Bromo-4-nitro-5-(or 7-)methyl-	4-Bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-
4.	2-Chloro-1-bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-	6-Chloro-4-nitro-5-(or 7-) methyl-	4-Chloro-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-
5.	1-Chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-3-methyl-	4:6-Dinitro-5-(or 7-) methyl-	2:4:6-Trinitro-3-methyl-

TABLE II

*Triazole.	% Yield by		M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
	Method I.	Method II.					
1.	65	18	225	Light yellow	C ₇ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br	Br: 29.41% **M: 272.50	29.30% 273.00
2.	60	14	218	Pink	C ₇ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 15.31 M: 227.90	15.53 228.50
3.	79	70	204	Cream	C ₇ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br	Br: 29.18 M: 272.30	29.30 273.00
4.	76	68	195°	Golden yellow	C ₇ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 15.62 M: 227.10	15.53 228.50
5.	48	20	191	Golden orange	C ₇ H ₅ O ₂ N ₆	N: 29.41 M: 238.87	29.28 239.00

* Number corresponds to those recorded in Table I.

** M denotes mol. wt.

TABLE III

Acetyl derivatives.

*Triazole.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	Colorless	155°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Br	Br: 24.91%	25.39%
2.	"	132°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 12.80	13.12
3.	"	145	C ₉ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Br	Br: 25.14	25.39
4.	"	140°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 12.9	* 13.12
5.	Light yellow	175°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₄ N ₆	N: 25.18	24.91

* The number of the triazole derivatives corresponds to those listed in Table I.

*Conversion of a Halogenonitromethylhydroxybenzotriazole to a
Dihalogenomethylhydroxybenzotriazole*

Reduction.—A solution of the nitrohydroxytriazole (0.4 M) in ethanol, HCl (conc.), and iron in requisite amounts were refluxed for 2½ hours. After filtration the solution was made alkaline with NaOH and the alcohol removed. The precipitated iron hydroxide was separated, the filtrate was acidified with HCl, and evaporated to dryness. The amino compound formed was not isolated; the residue was used as such in the subsequent preparations.

Diazotisation and Replacement of the Diazo Group by Halogen Atom.—The residue was dissolved in water (10 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 15 c.c.) was added. The mass was cooled in an ice bath and diazotised with aqueous sodium nitrite (4 g.). Reduced copper (0.2 g.) was added to the filtrate and the mixture was left overnight. Again the product was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue on crystallisation from water furnished dihalogenomethyl-1-hydroxy-1:2:3-benzotriazole.

To substitute the amino group by a bromine atom, hydrobromic acid instead of hydrochloric acid was employed. When two amino groups were to be replaced by two chlorine atoms, double the quantities of hydrochloric acid and sodium nitrite (required for diazotisation) were used.

The products 1, 3 and 4 mentioned in the following table were found to be identical; so were 2 and 5. As in the dihalogenated triazoles No. 4 and 5 the methyl group is in position 7, it is confirmed that in the triazoles No. 1, 2 and 3 also, methyl group occupies the same position.

TABLE IV

No.	Triazole.	Dihalogenated triazole formed.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.	Positi ⁿ of Me.
1.	6-Chloro-4-nitro-5-(or 7-) methyl-	4,6-Dichloro-5(or 7)-methyl-	206°	Colorless	C ₇ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂	Cl: 32.42	32.56	7
2.	6-Bromo-4-nitro-5-(or 7-) methyl-	4,6-Dibromo-5(or 7)-methyl-	210°	..	C ₇ H ₆ ON ₂ Br ₂	Br: 52.23	52.11	7
3.	4,6-Dinitro-5-(or 7-) methyl-	4,6-Dichloro-5 (or 7)-methyl-	205°	..	C ₇ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂	Cl: 32.68	32.56	7
4.	4-Chloro-6-nitro-7-methyl-	4,6-Dichloro-7-methyl-	206°	..	C ₇ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂	Cl: 32.38	32.56	
5.	4-Bromo-6-nitro-7-methyl-	4,6-Dibromo-7-methyl-	210°	..	C ₇ H ₆ ON ₂ Br ₂	Br: 52.39	52.11	